
160. More on diffuse interstellar bands

GAIA DATA RELEASE 3 was issued in June 2022, and the next major release, DR4, is not scheduled until 2025. But on 10 October 2023, the Gaia Data Processing and Analysis Consortium (DPAC) published five papers forming part of a special ‘**Focused Product Release**’. I looked at the first three in essays 157–159.

The fourth, by Schultheis et al. (2023), concerns further detailed spatial mapping of two diffuse interstellar bands, or DIBs. I will explain the context, describe the data used, and summarise their main results.

IHAVE ALREADY devoted a previous essay (essay 92, October 2022) to some early results on the mapping of DIBs with Gaia. Let me summarise a few key points, but refer to that essay for further background.

Briefly, DIBs are absorption features seen in stellar spectra, superimposed on a smoother wavelength-dependent interstellar extinction. They were first reported just over a century ago, but their origins still remain something of a mystery. Several hundred bands have now been discovered, at ultraviolet, visible and infrared wavelengths (e.g. Fan et al., 2019). And while there is a general consensus that they are probably due to large and complex molecules in the Galactic interstellar medium, only one carrier has been securely identified: ionised buckminsterfullerene (C_{60}^+), with five absorption bands in the near-infrared (Linnartz et al., 2020).

The choice of wavelength range for Gaia’s radial velocity spectrometer was driven by a number of considerations (see essay 85). Amongst these, and within the adopted wavelength range (845–872 nm), was a known medium-intensity DIB at 862 nm, first identified in 1975. The correlation of its equivalent width with absorption was known to be rather tight, suggesting that it could be used to build a detailed reddening map, especially for high values of interstellar extinction (Munari, 1999).

The first major study of the 862 nm DIB, from Gaia DR3, was reported by Schultheis et al. (2023). Their sample contained 476 117 stars with valid DIB measures, with their high-quality sample comprising 141 103 stars. The former was, by an order of magnitude, the largest homogeneous full-sky sample obtained to date.

ALTHOUGH THE strong line at 862 nm was the only confirmed DIB in Gaia’s RVS spectral range at the time of its consideration, Munari et al. (2008) also considered a weaker one at 864.8 nm to be another candidate. From 8458 DR3 spectra, Zhao et al. (2022) confirmed its existence, and showed that both equivalent widths are well correlated, albeit with the 862 nm line being better correlated with the E(BP–RP) extinction.

That is, in outline, the status of the DIB investigations with Gaia until the present ‘Focused Product Release’ study reported by Schultheis et al. (2023).

THE LATEST STUDY, by Schultheis et al. (2023) makes use of same DR3 data, but with an improved ‘pipeline’ treatment of the relevant RVS spectra to address two major limitations of the earlier studies.

The first was that, due to the limited signal-to-noise ratio of the individual RVS spectra, the 862.1 nm DIB could be successfully measured in only about 10% of the sources. Restricting the sample to more reliable high-quality measurements further reduced the sample size to around 140 000 sources. Another limitation was in the use of synthetic spectra in extracting the DIB signal.

Galactic distributions of the two DIBs at a distance $d = 1.53$ kpc. Other distance distributions are given in the study paper.

SCHULTHEIS ET AL. (2003) have developed a new module within DPAC Coordination Unit 8, responsible for source classification and parameterisation (essay 89). The module, DIB-SPEC, processed all 6.8 million RVS spectra, and made the new DIB measurements.

Based on the RVS spectral quality, and the results of the existing CU8 processing module GSP-SPEC, DIB-SPEC constructs two samples: a set of ‘target’ stars whose spectra are expected to contain possible DIB signals, and a set of 160 000 ‘reference’ stars, at high Galactic latitudes ($|b| \geq 65^\circ$), and covering a wide range of stellar parameters, less likely to contain DIB features.

The reference stars effectively define the corresponding contribution from the ISM spectra for each target star. Matching each target spectrum to its closest reference spectra in stellar parameter space then allows an empirical removal of the stellar spectrum, i.e. without reference to stellar models, and leaving a set of 6 million spectra characterising the interstellar medium (ISM).

Using the sky coordinates and parallax distances, they then assigned each ISM spectrum to a 3-d grid (of ‘Volume pIXELS’, or ‘voxels’) defined by Galactic coordinate and heliocentric distance, with an angular size of 1.8° (level 5 HEALPix), and 29 unequally sized distance shells. DIB-SPEC then stacks the spectra of the target stars within a given ‘voxel’, and fits the two DIBs in the stacked ISM spectra.

DIB-SPEC measures both DIB signals (at 862.1 nm and 864.8 nm) out to larger distances than DR3, so defining the large-scale spatial distribution of the DIB carriers. The results included in this specific ‘Focused Product Release’ include the best-fit parameters of the two DIBs (depth, central wavelength, width, and equivalent width), along with the stacked ISM spectra (i.e. containing only the interstellar features) in each voxel.

The width of the DIB profile, for example, contains substantial information about the properties of the intervening ISM clouds and the DIB carriers, such as the profile broadening that is related to the gas kinetic and rotational temperature in different physical environments.

AMONGST THEIR conclusions, they found that the strength and spatial distribution of the 862.1 nm DIB in the stacked spectra are consistent with what was found from Gaia DR3, but with a much higher signal-to-noise ratio, a higher spatial resolution, and extending to much larger distances. This allowed them to trace DIBs in the outer spiral arm, and beyond the Scutum–Centaurus spiral arm.

They produced all-sky maps, below Galactic latitudes $\pm 65^\circ$, and out to ~ 4000 pc, of both DIB features and their correlations. They found a reasonable correlation between the dust reddening found from stellar absorption and the equivalent widths of both DIBs. And they detected the signals of the 862.1 nm feature inside the Local Bubble (≤ 200 pc).

AT PRESENT, this significant advance in mapping these two specific DIBs, out to much larger distances, nevertheless leaves their origin as an unknown!

Example fits to the 862.1 nm and 864.8 nm DIBs (red lines) in stacked ISM spectra for five distance voxels in one direction.